

loam textured Entic Chromustert with $\text{KMnO}_4\text{-N}$ 110 ppm, 0.75% organic C, and pH 7.4. Test crop was ADT36, grown in 20-m² plots replicated 3 times in a randomized complete block design.

A 12.5- × 35-cm cylindrical frame covered with a polythene bag was placed between rows immediately after fertilizer application. A petri dish containing 100 ml of 0.1 N H_2SO_4 was suspended inside the frame. The dish was emptied at 3-d intervals and the contents distilled for NH_3 . Ammonia volatilization loss was calculated 15 d after basal application and after each topdressing (see table).

Values are after deducting loss in control plots. Correlations were worked out for pH, temperature, and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ content of floodwater with volatilization loss.

The cumulative N loss ranged from 3.44 to 5.85 kg/ha. The highest was with urea split application, followed by split-applied lac-coated urea. Green manure

Volatilization loss of N. TNRRI, Aduthurai, India, 1984.

Treatment	Loss of N (kg/ha)			Cumulative loss of N kg/ha
	Phase I 0-15 d	Phase II 16-30 d	Phase III 31-45 d	
Urea best split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	2.82	2.24	0.80	5.85
Urea all basal	3.13	1.28	0.50	4.95
Lac-coated urea (LCU) basal	2.89	1.35	0.48	4.72
Neem cake coated urea (NCU) basal	2.78	1.19	0.47	4.39
Green manure + urea (1 : 1) basal	2.20	1.11	0.47	3.78
LCU split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	2.34	2.15	0.57	5.06
NCU split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{4}$)	1.71	1.88	0.74	4.33
Green manure + urea split ($\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{8} + \frac{1}{8}$)	1.18	1.79	0.48	3.44
Mean	2.37	1.62	0.57	
CD				0.47
% loss to the total loss	52	36	12	100

and urea combination had relatively lower loss than other N sources. Basal application showed higher losses than topdressings. Of the total volatilization loss, 52% occurred within 15 d, 36% between 15 and 30 d, and 12% between 31 and 45 d. NH_3 loss correlated with

morning floodwater pH ($r = 0.45^{**}$), evening floodwater pH ($r = 0.55^{**}$), morning floodwater temperature ($r = 0.49^{**}$), evening floodwater temperature ($r = 0.61^{**}$), and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ content of floodwater ($r = 0.43^{**}$). □

Response of upland rice to nitrogen

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Three upland rice varieties (Faro 11, E425 and R66) were planted on sandy loam soil with 0.09% total N, 1.63%

organic matter, and pH 5.4. N as ammonium sulfate was applied at 0, 30, and 60 kg N/ha, half at planting and half 60 d after. P and K were applied basally, each at 30 kg/ha.

Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plot size was 12 m². Plant spacing was 30 × 30 cm.

Application of 60 kg N/ha did not significantly increase grain yield over 30 kg N/ha (Table 1). Stem borer damage and lodging percentage were higher with 60 kg N/ha.

Varieties tested were similar in all parameters examined (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of N level on yield, yield components, and growth of rice.^a Ibadan, Nigeria, 1984.

N level (kg/ha)	Yield (kg/plot)	Lodging ^b (%)	Whiteheads (no./plot)	Wt of 10 panicles (g)	Plant ht ^b (cm)	Tillers ^b (no./hill)
0	1.64 b	0	31 b	46 b	102 b	14 b
30	1.94 a	31	41 b	50 b	111 a	15 b
60	1.98 a	78	91 a	62 a	113 a	16 a

^a Mean of 3 replications. ^b Recorded at maturity. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Table 2. Varietal differences in yield, yield components, and growth of rice. Ibadan, Nigeria, 1984.

Variety	Yield (kg/plot)	Lodging (%)	Days to 50% flowering	Whiteheads (no./plot)	Wt of 10 panicles (g)	Plant ht (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)
Faro 11	1.87	39	87	55	52	107	15
E425	1.93	36	88	53	53	108	15
R66	1.78	33	88	54	52	110	15
LSD (0.05)	ns	-	-	ns	ns	ns	ns

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Relationship between organic N fraction and N uptake of rice in submerged soil

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A field experiment during the 1983-84 wet season showed that hydrolyzable

Correlations between N uptake and organic N fractions (hydrolyzable and nonhydrolyzable N).^a Pantnagar, India, 1983-84 wet season.

Plant N uptake	Hydrolyzable N				Nonhydrolyzable N			
	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT
15 DT	-0.331	-	-	-	-0.116	-	-	-
30 DT	0.702**	0.500	-	-	-0.115	0.331	-	-
45 DT	0.853**	0.743**	0.594*	-	-0.175	0.321	-0.405	-
60 DT	0.870**	0.805**	0.659*	0.436	-0.051	0.339	-0.387	-0.640*
(50% flowering)								
At harvest	0.862**	0.829**	0.667**	0.468	-0.118	0.338	-0.424	-0.641*

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. DT = days after transplanting.

Effect of nitrogen on rice in an alkali soil

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We studied the effect of N on rice variety Damodar (CSR1) in a highly barren alkali soil without amendment during 1981-1982 wet seasons. Soil was sandy-loam with pH 10.4, 91% exchangeable Na, 0.32 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/ 100 g, 40 kg available N/ha, 18 kg Olsen's extractable

P, and adequate K in the 0-15 cm layer.

Spacing was 15 × 15 cm with 3 seedlings/hill. N as urea was applied one-third at transplanting and the remainder as 2 equal splits at 25 and 50 d after transplanting; zinc sulfate was applied at 5.5 kg Zn/ ha. The rice was harvested 17 Nov 1981 and 16 Nov 1982.

Yield attributes and grain and straw yields significantly increased with N level (Table 1). Grain and straw N also increased significantly up to 120 kg N/ha (Table 2). Soil pH was not

organic N (6 N HCl extractable) is ultimately responsible for N in submerged soil. Hydrolyzable organic N up to 45 d after transplanting (DT) and N uptake of the rice crop at different growth stages (except N uptake at 15 DT) showed significant positive correlation (see table). The trend was reversed for nonhydrolyzable organic N except at 30 DT. □

Table 2. Influence of N level on N content of grain and straw of Darnodar grown in an alkali soil. Karnal, India, 1981-82.

N level (kg/ha)	Nitrogen content (kg/ha)			
	1981		1982	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
0	1.12	0.39	1.17	0.32
60	1.30	0.46	1.25	0.39
120	1.37	0.49	1.37	0.44
180	1.45	0.49	1.40	0.46
CD (0.05)	0.09	0.03	0.06	0.04

affected by N level, but decreased with cultivation. □

Table 1. Effect of nitrogen in an alkali soil on yield attributes and yield of Damodar (CSR1). Karnal, India, 1981-82.

N (kg/ha)	1981					1982					Soil pH after rice 1982
	Height (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		Height (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		
				Grain	Straw				Grain	Straw	
0	81.1	7.1	15.4	1.1	2.1	88.8	6.3	14.8	1.2	1.9	9.9
60	94.8	10.6	17.1	2.2	3.8	105.1	10.8	16.5	2.5	4.3	9.8
120	104.0	12.2	17.9	2.7	4.6	112.6	12.0	16.9	3.2	5.4	9.8
180	108.7	13.7	18.3	3.2	5.2	116.1	13.3	17.7	3.6	6.0	9.8
CD (0.05)	4.4	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.8	3.3	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.6	-

Consequences

Energy management in rice production

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We estimated total energy input and energy-use balance and efficiency in rice

production in relation to farm size in six randomly selected villages of Karnal district, Haryana State, north India. The farm households were categorized into five Strata on the basis of operational holding size (Cumulative Frequency Square Root method). Input-output data on the rice crop were gathered from 119 farmers (10% of the total population) representing the strata: 31

marginal (up to 1.0 ha), 26 small (1.1-2.0 ha), 29 lower medium (2.1-4.0 ha), 20 upper medium (4.1-6.0 ha), and 13 large (more than 6.0 ha).

In general, farmyard manure (FYM) and chemical fertilizers (stock resources), followed by labor and machinery (flow resources), were the most important energy inputs to rice production (Table 1). FYM and